

Study of Some Ternary Complexes in Solution

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Mixed ligand formation constants K_{MAL} (where $M = \text{Cu}^{2+}$, Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+} ; $A = \text{dipyridyl}$; $L = \text{catechol}$, pyrogallol or $\text{protocatechuic acid}$) have been determined by using a modified form of Irving-Rossotti technique. Values of K_{MAL} have been found to be very close to K_{ML} in Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+} and $K_{MAL} > K_{ML}$ in Cu(II) system. This relationship has been explained in terms of charge neutralization, interaction and favourable geometry.

Studies of the formation constants of the transition metal complexes with polyhydroxy phenols and phenolic acids have been carried out earlier. Cu^{2+} complexes of catechol have been studied by polarographic¹⁻² and potentiometric methods³⁻⁵. Athavale and coworkers⁶ studied Cu(II) , Zn(II) , Ni(II) and Cd(II) complexes of catechol and protocatechuic acid by using Calvin-Bjerrum titration technique. Formation constants of bivalent Cu , Zn , and Ni chelates of catechol have also been determined by Murakámi and coworkers⁷. However, study of mixed ligand systems using dipyriddy as primary ligand and the polyhydroxy phenols as the secondary ligands is not much⁸⁻⁹. In the present paper an attempt has been made to study the K_{MAL} of systems, (where $M = \text{Co}^{2+}$, Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+} ; $A = \text{dipyridyl}$ and $L = \text{catechol}$, pyrogallol , $2,3\text{-dihydroxynaphthalene}$ and $\text{protocatechuic acid}$) using a modified form of Irving-Rossotti titration technique¹⁰⁻¹¹. The first formation constants K_{ML_1} , of the binary metal ligand systems have been determined under similar experimental conditions as used in the mixed ligand system and K_{MAL_1} and K_{MAL_2} have also been determined in case of Zn^{2+} , Co^{2+} and Cd^{2+} complexes by using Irving-Rossotti titration technique, for the sake of comparison with mixed ligand formation constants. The studies with Cu^{2+} and Ni^{2+} complexes using excess of ligand have already been reported.^{12,13,14}

EXPERIMENTAL

Ligands were all A.R. pure. Metal perchlorates were prepared and analysed. Other reagents were sodium perchlorate (Fluka), perchloric acid (Baker analysed) and sodium hydroxide (Chemapol Czechoslovakia). All solutions were prepared in conductivity water. Metrohm pH meter with a readability of ± 0.05 was used for pH measurements. The thermostatic bath temperature was maintained at $30^\circ (\pm 0.1^\circ)$.

The formation constants of binary Zn^{2+} -ligand, Cd^{2+} -ligand, Co^{2+} -ligand systems were determined by preparing solutions, carrying out pH titration and calculating in accordance with Irving-Rossotti titration technique.¹⁰ The values of proton ligand and metal ligand formation constants obtained by the linear plot method¹⁵ have been tabulated (Table 1 and 2).

TABLE 1

Proton ligand formation constants of secondary ligands. $t = 30^\circ$.

Ligand	P_{K_1H}	P_{K_2H}	P_{K_3H}
Catechol	11.30	9.00	—
Pyrogallol	10.35	8.65	—
Protocatechuic acid	12.25	8.95	4.54
2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene	12.50	8.70	—

TABLE 2

Stability constants of secondary ligand chelates. $t = 30^\circ$

Ligand	Cu		Ni		Zn		Cd		Co	
	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$								
Catechol	12.97	10.16	7.80	5.32	8.24	8.95	6.86	4.39	7.00	—
Pyrogallol	12.88	—	7.07	—	7.64	—	6.14	—	—	—
Protocatechuic acid	14.17	10.91	8.77	—	9.11	6.68	8.07	—	8.00	5.46
2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene	14.42	11.75	9.72	6.95	9.92	7.57	8.54	5.90	8.59	7.36

For the mixed ligand systems, solutions were prepared as follows :

1. 0.02M perchloric acid, 0.180M NaClO₄
2. 0.02M perchloric acid, 0.002M dipyridyl, 0.178M NaClO₄
3. 0.02M perchloric acid, 0.002M dipyridyl, 0.002M metal perchlorate, 0.0176M NaClO₄
4. 0.02M perchloric acid, 0.002M secondary ligand, 0.178M NaClO₄
5. 0.02M perchloric acid, 0.002M dipyridyl, 0.002M secondary ligand, 0.002M metal perchlorate, 0.174M NaClO₄
6. 0.02M perchloric acid, 0.002M secondary ligand, 0.002M metal perchlorate, 0.176M NaClO₄.

In each case the total volume was made upto 50 ml. and ionic strength was initially raised to 0.2M. The plots of pH against volume of alkali have been represented (fig. 1, 2 and 3) in case of dipyridyl catechol systems of Ni(II), Zn(II), Cd(II). Cu-dipy catecholate, having been worked out by the same method earlier,¹¹ curve for Cu-dipy pyrogallol is being presented in fig. 4. The nature of the curves are similar in other systems.

The third and sixth curves (fig. 1-4) are same as ligand and ligand+metal curves in Irving-Rossotti titration, except for the fact that an excess of ligand has been avoided. Metal ion and ligand are in 1 : 1 ratio as in the mixed ligand system and hence $\log K_{ML_1}$

can be obtained under similar conditions as for $\log K_{MAL}$. Values of $\log K_{ML_1}$ have been calculated using the same method¹³ of linear plot as above. The values of K_{ML_1} obtained in case of Cd^{2+} and Zn^{2+} complexes are same as those in Table 2. In case of Cu^{2+} and Ni^{2+} complexes also values of $\log K_{ML_1}$ are in agreement with the values of $\log K_1$ reported earlier^{13,14}.

Fig. No. 1, 2, 3 :

1. Acid
2. Dipyrldyl
3. Catechol
4. 1 : 1 molar of M^{2+} to dipyrldyl
5. 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratio of M^{2+} to dipyrldyl and catechol
6. 1 : 1 molar ratio of M^{2+} to catechol.

Fig. No. 4 :

1. Acid
2. Dipyrldyl
3. Pyrogallol
4. 1 : 1 molar of M^{2+} to dipyrldyl
5. 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratio of M^{2+} to dipyrldyl and pyrogallol
6. 1 : 1 molar ratio of M^{2+} to pyrogallol.

An observation of mixed ligand system curves (fig. 1, 2, 3 and 4) shows that metal dipyrldyl curve (4) diverges from the dipyrldyl curve (2) at low pH indicating that metal dipyrldyl complex formation takes place at low pH . The calculation of \bar{n} shows that it continues to be one upto $pH \sim 6$ after which metal dipyrldyl curve diverges from the dipyrldyl curve showing formation of hydroxy complex $[M(\text{dipyrldyl})(OH)_2]$. After pH 9.5 the

complex decomposes forming metal hydroxides which precipitate out indicating that the metal dipyriddy complex 1 : 1 formed at low pH is stable upto high pH . Metal dipyriddy phenolic ligand curve (5) and metal dipyriddy curve (4) overlap each other at low pH . This indicates that in the pH range where dipyriddy combines with metal, combination of polyhydroxy phenolic ligand does not take place. Since the dissociations of the ligands catechol and pyrogallol at low pH is negligible, the curve (4) and (5) overlap. In case of protocatechuic acid, the metal dipyriddy+protocatechuic acid curve (5) separates from metal+dipy. curve (4) due to self dissociation of carboxylic group. In cases of all the ligands, however, curve (5) diverges from the ligand curve (3), after $pH \sim 4.5$ in copper system and at ~ 6.5 in Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+} systems. In this range combination of secondary ligand with metal dipyriddy starts. The reaction can be represented as follows :

since the dissociation of M-dipyriddy does not take place in the range of association of the secondary ligand it can be considered that the secondary ligand combines with (M-dipyriddy) $^{2+}$ just as it does with (M-aq) $^{2+}$ in simple system. In case of Cu^{2+} system the combination of secondary ligand is completed before the pH where $[Cu(dipyriddy)(OH)_2]$ is formed. In case of Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+} the secondary ligands adds in the same pH range where $[Ni(dipyriddy)(OH)_2]$ formation takes place. In the presence of complexing secondary ligand, formation of $[M(dipyriddy)(OH)_2]$ is suppressed. Formation constant of mixed ligand systems $[(Zn-dipyriddy-glycollic\ acid)]$ where glycollic acid combines at higher pH has also been determined by earlier workers¹⁶, considering that $[Zn(dipyriddy)(OH)_2]$ is not formed in presence of glycollic acid. As such the horizontal distance between curves (3) and (5) can be measured and used for calculation of \bar{n} ; where \bar{n} is the average number of phenolic ligands associated with one (M-dipyriddy) $^{2+}$. The equation for the calculation will be the same as in the original paper¹³

$$\bar{n} = \frac{(V''' - V'')(N + E^0 + T^2_L(Y - \bar{n}_H))}{(V^0 + V'')\bar{n}_H T^0_m}$$

Here T^0_m is the concentration of (M dipyriddy) $^{2+}$ which is equal to the concentration of M^{2+} . \bar{n} and pL were calculated at different pH . At $\bar{n} = 0.5$ in the formation curve $pL = \log K_{MAL}$. More precise values were obtained by using the method of linear plot¹². The values have been presented in table 3.

TABLE 3

Stability constants of mixed ligand chelates ($t = 30^\circ$)

Ligand (L)	$\log K$ CuDipy CuDipyL	$\log K$ NiDipy NiDipyL	$\log K$ ZnDipy ZnDipyL	$\log K$ CdDipy CdDipyL
Catechol	13.27	7.69	7.81	6.43
Pyrogallol	13.08	6.90	7.35	—
Protocatechuic acid	15.48	8.61	8.75	7.51

Titration could not be done in mixed ligand systems with 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene because the heterochelate gets precipitated. In case of Cd-dipy pyrogallol system also \bar{n} does not go beyond 0.15 and hence K_{MAL} could not be calculated. Mixed ligand study could not be possible in case of cobalt complexes because the mixed ligand curve (5) shows a wide separation from the secondary ligand curve (3). This may be due to some additional reaction absorbing -OH groups and hence the present method is not applicable for the study of such systems.

DISCUSSION

An observation of simple system values indicates that the order of formation constants of the complexes of the different ligands with a metal is

The order is in accordance with the basicities of the ligand in case of catechol, pyrogallol and 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene. These are all bidentate and coordination takes place from two ortho-hydroxy groups. In case of protocatechuic acid also it has been established that the coordination takes place from two ortho-hydroxy group^{16,17}. The +ve inductive effect of COO⁻ group lowers down the dissociation of the OH⁻ groups and thus increases the tendency of the ligand to form complexes. Higher stability of protocatechuic acid complexes of metals has been observed earlier¹³. This has been attributed to a π interaction involving metal $d\pi$ orbitals, lone pair orbitals of oxygen atom and ring delocalized π orbitals. This M-L π interaction is more, greater the acidity of the ligand. This explains the high values of protocatechuate complexes. The order of the stability constants of the complexes of different metal ions is as follows :

This is in accordance with Irving-Williams order¹⁸. The log K_1 values of cobalt (II) and nickel (II) are very close to one another. The higher formation constant values of Co(II) complexes may be due to partial oxidation of Co(II) to Co(III). The higher values of the formation constants of Zn(II) complexes than Ni(II) complexes, in case of phenolic ligands, has been observed earlier⁶. It can be explained to be due to greater M-L π interaction between the π orbitals of Zn²⁺ and the ligand. Cd(II) with a bigger ionic radius will form weak L-M σ bond and hence forms less stable complexes.

It is interesting to observe the values of mixed ligand formation constants K_{MAL} . The order is almost same as in the case of simple system. The value of K_{MAL} is higher than the simple system value K_{ML_1} in case of copper. This has been observed earlier^{8,19}. In case of other complexes also K_{MAL} is nearly equal to K_{ML_1} . It has been observed that in cases where $A = \text{en, NTA or EDTA}$, log K_{MAL} is significantly lower than K_{ML_1} .⁷ Dipyriddy though a neutral ligand has a higher tendency to coordinate with metal ions than water. Hence in $[\text{M}(\text{dipyridyl})(\text{aq})]^{2+}$ chelates the concentration of electron around the metal ion will be more than in simple $[\text{M}(\text{aq})]^{2+}$, and hence the constant corresponding to the reaction $[\text{CuA}]^{2+} + \text{L}$ should be less than the constant for $\text{Cu}^{2+} + \text{L}$. In the present investigation however, $K_{MAL} \sim K_{ML_1}$. This can be attributed to the fact that M-N bond

in M dipyrityl is not due to L-M, bond alone but there is some amount of M-L, $d\pi-p\pi$ interaction, which does not allow the concentrations of electrons to increase significantly. The tendency of $[M\text{ aq}]^{2+}$ or $[M\text{ dipy aq}]^{2+}$ to receive the secondary ligand remains almost same. The value of $\log K_{MAL}$ also goes up because of the formation of neutral species $[MAL]$ with favourable entropy and enthalpy effects⁸. Siegel and Coworkers¹⁹ explained the higher values of $\log K_{MAL}$ than $\log K_{ML_1}$, in case of copper complexes by considering that dipyrityl with strong ligand field effect reduces $[\text{Cu}(\text{dipy})(\text{OH})_2]$ to square planar geometry and thus facilitates the addition of secondary ligands. This effect added to π interaction and charge neutralization effect results in $K_{MAL} > K_{ML_1}$.

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